

PREPARING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO THINK INDEPENDENTLY

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Abstract. *This article discusses ways to increase the effectiveness of knowledge by activating school-aged students in the course of the lesson, organizing their independent work.*

Keywords: *pupil, educational process, independent education, knowledge efficiency, assessment, motivation.*

Despite the large number of types of organization of the educational process at school and the various vagueness, each of them solves a certain set of didactic issues and fulfills its task. Their diversity actually informs about the creativity and skills of teachers of schools and higher educational institutions, and indicates that they benefit from the effectiveness of their work. Therefore, it is definitely inappropriate to evaluate their potential and their actions in the process of their talent in the same position. There is also a big difference in the potential of students' independent work and thinking.

Students' independent work, first of all, preparation for it is created by the teacher in such ways as problem-based presentation of materials. In this case, the following assignments can be regularly recommended: study of the material based on the textbook, sample independent exercises, new types of assignments, creative works. Independent activity increases activity, teaching students to work independently has a good effect. Independent activity makes a person alert and responsive. This activity should be developed harmoniously among schoolchildren of younger age.

One of the qualities of mental development of students is that they complete the tasks by remembering them completely. Special attention is paid to the ability to independently find and correct mistakes made while understanding (imagining) the purpose of the work to be performed, defining its plan and choosing the work method. It is useful to choose convenient methods for the students to complete tasks quickly and correctly, and to recommend basic words by asking leading questions to organize it. It is natural that students have difficulties in performing independent work in a quality manner. Because their imaginations are still bright and their vocabulary is not enough. It is known that a child receives education from the family for the first time. The social environment in the family shows that its internal order discipline consciously educates the child.

The following should be followed when teaching students for independent activities:

- each assignment should be suitable for students' abilities and should be able to arouse interest;
- the work should be directed from easy to difficult, from simple to complex, and should be understandable to the student;
- let the children feel self-confidence in doing the work, let them feel boldness in themselves when starting work;
- independent tasks should be done one by one, of course, attention should be paid to the student who is learning freely.

- it is necessary to pay particular attention to changing the type of assignments by always taking turns;

- it is necessary to remind that everyone should start the tasks at the same time and finish them at a certain time, and accustom the children who are busy to fulfill this requirement;

- the workplace should always be comfortable and tidy (there should be no extra things on the desk);

- assignments can be completed at different stages of the lesson;

- it is desirable to be consistent in working with textbooks and didactic materials.

As much as possible, it is necessary to teach children the basic knowledge and skills in the classroom, and to regulate homework assignments. That's why homework should be easy, mainly to encourage children to observe.

- Wide use of new pedagogical, modern technologies, non-traditional methods in lessons;

- Extensive use of demonstration, didactic, test, distribution materials; - Be friendly to students;

- Paying attention to the quality and efficiency of studies;

- Using various exercises to teach students to think freely and independently;

- Pay special attention to speech development;

- Use of new information technologies;

- Organization of circles such as "Expressive reading";

- Conducting individual work with students who do not catch up in free time;

- Giving importance to Arabism in sciences.

When monitoring students' knowledge, special attention should be paid to students who have learned less. In primary grades, students are taught several types of reading, that is, conscious, fast, correct and expressive reading.

Independent activity increases activity, and teaching free-flowing students to work independently has a good effect. Independent activity makes the student alert and responsive. For this, first of all, it is necessary to mentally prepare students for independent work, to make sure that they can do something and do it well.

If the teacher gives each student confidence along with understanding to create the first sets, the student can make a plan for the work he is doing independently, see and correct the mistakes and shortcomings. It is useful to choose convenient methods for students to complete tasks quickly and correctly, to always ask leading questions and recommend key words to organize it.

Tools that form critical thinking appear as a system only when the choice is made, taking into account the specific goals of each stage in the educational process, and they together affect each component of critical thinking of primary school students. The content of critical thinking is connected through three external factors: object, purpose, didactic principles development. What should be understood by the didactic basis of the formation of critical thinking of primary school students? We understand this concept as follows:

1. Justify the goals of critical thinking.

2. Scientific development of the content of critical thinking of primary school students.

3. Scientific development of the formation of lesson motives.

4. Development of scientifically based and practical forms of students' critical thinking.

5. Scientific development of teaching methods, that is, scientific development of systems of methods of formation of critical thinking and methods of teaching students.

6. Development of a system of tools for forming students' critical thinking - textbooks, didactic materials, visual aids and technical tools.

7. Scientific development of organizing and managing critical thinking of primary school students.

The formation of critical thinking of elementary school students is a complex and long-term process. It is formed in the joint work of the teacher and the student. On this basis, on the basis of critical thinking, there is an opportunity to jointly consider all the important components of the formation of critical thinking of elementary school students (purpose, content, forms, methods and methods, tools and motives).

In conclusion, providing motivations, methods and organizational means of forming students' active critical thinking requires the need for deep research at different age stages of human development.

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